

**METAPHOR IN CHILDREN'S LITERATURE. GEORGE ORWELL'S
"ANIMAL FARM" AS AN EXAMPLE
(BASED ON UZBEKI AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES)**

Abduazimova Marjona Abdurazzoq qizi

Keldiyorova Musharraf Ulug'bek qizi

Students of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Scientific advisor: Mamayoqubova Shahlo

Teacher of the Department of English Language Theory and Literature,
Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Annotation: *It is known that the most important tool of children's literature is the word. It is delivered in a way that is understandable and effective through the means of artistic images. Metaphor is one of the most important tools of artistic representation. It is widely used not only in poetry but also in prose of children's literature. This article analyzes the use of this tool in children's literature and the ability of a writer or poet to use it in their works. We took George Orwell's "Animal Farm" as a research object.*

Keywords: *children's literature, fiction, artistic purpose, effect, tool, metaphor, simile, style, analysis, research.*

Introduction

Calling one word the other on the basis of the similarity of two things is called a metaphor (Greek. "metaphor"-transfer), and it serves to strengthen the meaning of the word. A thing takes the name of another thing that has the same characteristic according to its characteristics, shape, movement, color, smell, size, etc.

When the meaning of one word is transferred to another by the method of metaphor, the sign common to that subject remains in the concept. Metaphoric transfer of meaning occurs mostly in fiction. This makes the writer's opinion impressive and shows his artistic and aesthetic ability. That is why poets and writers make friends with such visual tools when creating artistic works.

A metaphor is a literary device that creates an imaginary comparison between two dissimilar things. In this, thing A, i.e. the subordinate word, ensures the creation of thing B, i.e. the governing word. Through this method of equation, metaphor helps to explain an unknown concept by colorfully relating it to a known concept; to concretize abstract ideas; and it helps to make incomprehensible concepts understandable. In addition, as a rhetorical tool, the work can attract the attention of readers and customers. We can show as an example the sentences he pours as initial information:

1. “Bill is an early bird” __ “Bill - erta qush”. (Usually applied to people who get up early in the morning.);
2. “Life is a highway” __ “Hayot bu katta yo‘l”. (Comparing life to a very long journey is often observed in English literature.);
3. “Her eyes were diamonds” __ “Uning ko‘zlari olmos edi”. (That is, his eyes shone and shone like diamonds.).

If you notice, metaphors are not always translated literally, but are translated according to the context in relation to the whole meaning.

Is a metaphor a simile?

Some language learners confuse metaphor with simile. In fact, they are completely different from each other. If a metaphor is preceded by auxiliary and form-forming adverbs such as *as*, *like*, it is not considered a metaphor, but a simile. For example:

Life is a highway – Metaphor.

Life is **like** rainbow – Simile.

It can sometimes be difficult to distinguish a metaphor from other artistic similes. That is why it is necessary to consider through many examples.

She’s **as** cute **as** a button.

It’s **like** shooting fish in a barrel.

He’s **as** nutty **as** a fruitcake.

In various sources, metaphor is considered as important for literature as a drop of water. Because writers or poets use metaphor a lot to give artistic color to their works or to create colorfulness. Sometimes a metaphor can be the translator of a whole sentence, and if this tool is removed, the text may lose its meaning. Metaphor performs the following tasks:

- Metaphors can make prose more muscular or imagery more vivid;
- Writers frequently turn to metaphors to describe people in unexpected ways;
- Metaphors can help “visualize” a situation or put an event in context;
- To entertain and tickle the brain, metaphor examples sometimes compare two extremely unlike things;
- Metaphors can help frame abstract concepts in ways that readers can easily grasp.

The main thing in this is the ability of the writer to use metaphors and distinguish them from the means of artistic representation, as well as the specific purpose of using this means. The reason is that it is important to clearly convey an abstract concept to the reader or to create sentences with many meanings using few words to prevent misunderstandings that the reader may encounter during the book reading process. For

example, let's take a work called "Animal Farm" by George Orwell. In the work, the writer skillfully used a metaphor based on the speech of animals.

Use and explanation of metaphor in the work:

1. All through that summer the work of the farm went **clockwork**. The animals were happy as they had never conceived it possible to be. Every mouthful of food was an **acute positive pleasure**, now that it was truly their own food, produced by themselves and for themselves, not doled out to them by a grudging master.

Butun yoz fermadagi ishlar xuddi **ish soati dek** bir xil vaqtda bo'ldi. (When used with an auxiliary such as metaphor in this sentence, it was considered a simile rather than a metaphor. However, auxiliaries can be used for clarity in the translation. The working hour metaphor expresses the sentences of working hours as always, the same, on time, i.e. 8/5.) Here, the metaphor serves to make the image or sentence more specific.

Hayvonlarni baxtiyor edilar, chunki ular hech qachon bunday bo'lishini tasavvur qilishmagan. Har bir luqma **o'tkir ijobiy rohat** edi. Ha bu ovqatlar o'zlari tomonidan o'zlari uchun tayyorlangan edi hamda uni hech qanday qizg'anchiq boshliq taqsimlab bermas edi. (In the above sentence, the word sharp is used in relation to the word taste. The word sharp is used to express the sharp nature of something. However, in fiction, as a descriptive tool, this word is used figuratively and is used to strengthen the meaning.)

2. Beasts of England, beasts of Ireland,
Hearken to my **joyful tidings**
Of **the golden future time**.
Soon or late **the day is coming**,
Tyrant Man shall be o'erthrown,
Angliyaning hayvonlari,
Irlandiya hayvonlari,
Quvonchli xabarimga quloq solinglar
U **Oltin kelajak** haqida.
Hademay o'sha **kun keladi**.
Zolim odamdan qutilamiz,

In the above-mentioned poetic sentence, metaphors are used for the purpose of increasing artistry. Sentences such as "**Joyful tidings**" and "**the golden future**" refer to a type of metaphor called a feature. Metaphors can make prose more muscular or

imagery more vivid and to entertain and tickle the brain, metaphor examples sometimes compare two extremely unlike things.

The sentence "**The day is coming**" uses the action meaning of the metaphor. Sometimes two dissimilar things are compared through this art form. Metaphors can help frame abstract concepts in ways that readers can easily grasp.

3. When Squealer went on to give further graphic details of Boxer's **death-bed**, the admirable care he had received, and the expensive medicines for which Napoleon had paid without a thought as to the cost, their last **doubts disappeared**. Chiyiltoq Boksching **o'lim to'shagidagi** qo'shimcha tafsilotlarni, uning qimmatbaho parvarishlarini va Napoleonning narxi haqida o'ylamasdan pul to'lagan qimmatbaho dori-darmonlarni keltirgani haqidagi tafsilotlarni batafsil keltirishda davom etganda, ularning so'nggi **shubhalari g'oyib bo'ldi**. The meaning of the phrase "Death-bed" is changed by the method of metaphor and serves to exaggerate the existing situation. The word "disappeared" changed its meaning according to the sign of movement.

4. **A cry of horror** burst from all the animals.

Barcha hayvonlardan **qo'rqinch ko'z yoshlari** otilib chiqdi. The writer used the phrase "**A cry of horror**" to express that those who are shedding tears are trembling with fear. Writers frequently turn to metaphors to describe people or their feelings in unexpected ways.

5. But no animal can escape the **cruel knife** in the end.

Lekin oxirida hech qaysi hayvon **shavqatsiz pichoqdan** qocha olmaydi.

In this sentence, the idea that the knife will kill them one day is expressed, and the word rude is used in relation to an inanimate object. In this sentence we see, writers frequently turn to metaphors to describe people in unexpected ways and metaphors can help us imagine the current situation "visualize" understand a situation or put an event in a specific context.

(Note, there is a synecdoche (part through whole) transfer of meaning through the expression "cruel knife". In other words, this sentence refers to a person who is rude).

6. And remember, comrades, your resolution must never **falter**. No argument must **lead** you astray.

Yodingizda tuting, safdoshlar, sizning qaroringiz hech qachon **zaiflashmaydi**. Hech qanday bir bahsingiz sizni egri yo'lga **boshlamaydi**. The metaphor used in this sentence is used to add imagery to the work of art. And the metaphor served to revive a certain word.

7. They had had **a hard year**, and after the sale of part and corn, the stores of food for the winter were none too plentiful, but the windmill compensated for everything.

Ular uchun o'sha **yil qattiq** kelgan edi, bug'doyning bir qismi sotib bo'lingach, qish uchun g'amlangan ovqat yetarli darajada emasligi ayon bo'ldi, lekin shamol tegirmoni kam ozuqani qoplay oldi. The metaphor presented in this sentence can help to visualize an existing situation, understand situations or put an event in a specific context.

It can be seen that by using metaphor, the writer managed to describe various situations in ways that the reader did not expect.

Conclusiona and suggestions

As noted above, metaphor connects two dissimilar or unrelated concepts. In order to attract the reader's attention, unexpected similes are used, the writer conveys abstract and incomprehensible situations to the reader through this method. In fiction, many writers sometimes use exaggeration to color the ideas they want to express. The reason is that the works attract the reader with their artistic similes. Especially when animating animals or inanimate objects, the use of such artistic means is required. Like other artistic representational tools, metaphor is a very powerful tool. Because, through the metaphor you use, you create a bridge between the reader's mind and your powerful image, and with this, you can make your every idea interesting and alive, and create the ground for the reader to freely imagine the hero and the world he lives in.

REFERENCES:

1. 90+ Metaphor Examples in Literature That You Need to Know. 19 October 2018.
2. A. Nurmonov, A. Sobirov, Sh. Yusupova; *Modern Uzbek literary language. Book 2. "ILM ZIYA" TASHKENT-2016.*
3. George Orwell "Animal farm". *New English Weekly*, 29 July 1937.
4. M. Jumayeva (2022). *CHARACTERISTICS OF VERBS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. Science and innovation, 1 (B7), 711-714. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7264531.*
5. M. Jumayeva (2022). *EFFECTIVE CREATIVE WAY OF ERKIN VAHIDOV. TRANSLATOR, POET, HERO OF UZBEKISTAN. Science and innovation, 1 (B5), 404-409. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7059373.*
6. M. Jumayeva (2022). *UYG'ONISH DAVRI ALLOMALARINING PEDAGOGIKA VA TA'LIMTARBIYAGA O'ZGACHA YONDASHUV ASOSIDAGI QARASHLARI TAHLILI. Science and innovation, 1 (B5), 26-29. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6990805.*
7. M. Jumayeva, & M. Jumayeva (2022). *THE IMPORTANCE OF FEATURE FILMS IN INCREASING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING. Science and innovation, 1 (B7), 581-583. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7257719.*
8. Maxmudjonov Ibroximjon, & Jumayeva Mukarrama. (2022). *HOZIRGI KUN YOSHLARINI IJTIMOYIY MUNOSABATLARGA KIRISHISHIDA CHET TILLARINI O'RGATILISHI VA UNING AHAMIYATI. Involta Scientific Journal, 1(5), 178–182. Retrieved from <https://involta.uz/index.php/iv/article/view/119>.*
9. *Metaphor - Literary Terms* literaryterms.net/metaphor.
10. *What is a Metaphor? - Definition and Examples | Grammarly* www.grammarly.com/blog
11. M. Jumayeva, J. Isheryakova, & M. Mahmudova (2022). *FAIRY TALES AS A PHENOMENON THAT PLAYS AN ESSENTIAL ROLE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE INTELLECT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN. Science and innovation, 1 (B8), 1080-1082. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7408925.*

